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Work-Life Balance and Interpersonal Support as Correlates to Emotional States

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Abstract

Among 100 remote workers in different departments in a company in Pasay City selected in this study, this study examined the relationship between their affective states, work-life balance, and interpersonal support. A descriptive-correlational study approach was used by the researcher. The Work-Related Quality of Life Scale, Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale, and Interpersonal Support and Evaluation List were the instruments employed. The results indicate that remote workers experience high levels of job and career satisfaction, which indicates their work-life balance. The remaining dimensions of work-life balance, including control at work, working conditions, tension, and general well-being, are balanced. In general, they also have high levels of interpersonal support in their line of work and can experience normal levels of stress and melancholy but with mild anxiety. Additionally, there is a negligible correlation between their work-life balance and interpersonal support, a substantial correlation between their work-life balance and emotional states, and a substantial correlation between their interpersonal support and emotional states. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) was employed to evaluate the hypothesis by examining the correlation between their affective states, interpersonal support, and work-life balance. It can be concluded that the respondents' current work-from-home arrangement has been advantageous to them, as they have realized that what can be accomplished in a face-to-face setting can be accomplished remotely. Similarly, it is advantageous to their emotional state, interpersonal relationships, and overall health. Additionally, the remote setup offered them emotional support, facilitating positive emotions development. The contentment they felt regarding their jobs and professions was also a result of the flexible schedule that was incorporated into their setup.

Keywords: *work-life balance, interpersonal support, emotional states*

Introduction

The global community encountered a pandemic in 2020, and the guidelines established by the government to combat the pandemic continue to present a challenge to the operations of business organizations. The increased number of COVID-19 cases has impacted the operations of numerous establishments, resulting in lockdowns and the closure of non-essential companies. As a result, physical contact and distancing within the company have been implemented. Many organizations and corporations were compelled to alter their work environments during the pandemic, transitioning from an office-based environment to a remote or home-based one.

Remote work during the pandemic has a significant impact on the work-life balance of employees, and it is a daily struggle to safeguard ourselves and our loved ones from the COVID-19 virus. Not only is the virus responsible for the anxiety and tension that employees experience, but also the abrupt alterations to their workplace. The challenge of fostering a balance between personal and professional life among employees is a challenge that companies that have transitioned to work from home for the first-time encounter. We have been humbled by the surge of inspirational new ideas that have been developed in response to the unprecedented challenges that this crisis has brought to both individuals and society. Innovation is more critical than it has ever been. The last few weeks and months have illuminated the potential of human creativity and collaboration, from the monitoring of critical data to neighborly acts of benevolence (Nesta, 2021).

Remote work experienced a significant moment when COVID-19 necessitated that companies worldwide dispatch their employees to work virtually from home. The Covid-19 pandemic has been a traumatic experience for over a year, and it has prompted numerous mental health concerns. However, the extent of this impact is likely to be greater for individuals who have been working remotely for years and have been sacrificing time with their families due to the tendency to juggle work and other priorities. Is the emotional state of remote laborers still stable and positive? What strategies do they employ to manage anxiety, tension, and depression? Additionally, how do remote professionals manage their time between work, family, and self-care? And how do remote workers receive interpersonal support from their family and peers? It is uncertain when this will conclude, and it is likely that companies will continue to establish work-from-home arrangements for their employees to maintain organizational objectives.

The employees' daily activities during work-from-home duties are also influenced by factors that are present in the new normal workplace set-up and working environment. The researcher endeavored to investigate the extent to which the emotional states and interpersonal support of remote workers influence their work-life balance in this study. Remote workers who have transitioned from a home-based work environment to a remote work environment since the onset of the pandemic have encountered varying adjustments in their daily lives. The researcher believed the work environment of an employee significantly influences their emotional states, interpersonal support, and work-life balance.

The majority of employees had limited experience with remote work prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, and neither they nor their organizations were adequately equipped to facilitate this practice. Currently, the unprecedented COVID-19 pandemic of 2020 has

necessitated the employment of millions of remote workers worldwide, resulting in a de facto global experiment in remote work (Kniffin et al., 2020). Almost immediately, remote work has become the "new normal." Personal and psychological consequences of home-based work include the development of strategies for working from home and the impact on one's personality. The current study revealed that a significant number of participants had devised a variety of strategies to manage stress and motivation isolation. These encompassed the following: the establishment of support networks with colleagues, the establishment of personal goals for the completion of work, the scheduling of social engagements with friends or family, the participation in regular social activities outside of the household, and the development of daily and/or weekly work schedules or timetables. Nevertheless, a significant number of individuals discovered that homeworking had personal consequences, including reduced social interaction, loneliness, a lack of self-esteem, and motivation. A professional mother who is employed by an international organization stated, "It is effortless to become demotivated while sitting in your office, as there is no one present to motivate you." Some homeworkers experienced fragmentation in their personal time. The protracted effects of pandemic-related restrictions have resulted in a common setting for many individuals to work from home, and they have also introduced mental health concerns of varying severity. Remote employees are subjected to a variety of challenges that can be stressful. However, the psychological effects of working from home are not yet fully understood, and minor stressors that are not managed can accumulate and have long-term negative consequences. The objective of this investigation is to identify potential strategies for mitigating the adverse effects of remote work, enhancing the work-life balance, and enhancing the mental health of remote employees.

Furthermore, this research will assist organizations and our field in industrial psychology in recognizing that remote workers require attention and should safeguard their mental health. Organizations should also be aware that remote workers are not productive 24/7 simply because they are working within their comfort zone. This study will serve as a reference and supplementary investigation for all practitioners who are confronted with the same challenge within their organizations. Providing remote workers with a program that can assist them in managing their emotional states, adjustment style, and work-life balance during the work-from-home setup is one of the most critical actions that employers can take. A productivity program for employees can assist them in adjusting to the new normal, making their employment thrilling and enjoyable, while also facilitating the management of their emotional states and work-life balance.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the relationship between work-life balance, interpersonal support, and emotional states among selected employees in a real estate company in Pasay City.

1. What is the level of work-life balance among the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. General well-being;
 - 1.2. Home-work Interface;
 - 1.3. Job and Career Satisfaction
 - 1.4. Control at Work
 - 1.5. Work Conditions
 - 1.6. Stress at Work
2. What is the level of interpersonal support of the respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1. Tangible Support
 - 2.2. Belonging Support
 - 2.3. Self-esteem Support
 - 2.4. Appraisal Support
3. What is the level of emotional states among the respondents in terms of:
 - 3.1. Depression
 - 3.2. Anxiety; and
 - 3.3. Stress
4. Is there a significant relationship between work-life balance and interpersonal support among the respondents?
5. Is there a significant relationship between work-life balance and emotional states among the respondents?
6. Is there a significant relationship between interpersonal support and emotional states among the respondents?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a quantitative approach. A descriptive-correlational study approach was used by the researcher. Morling (2018) states that descriptive methods are used to summarize and organize data, while correlational designs include measuring variables and testing their relationships. A descriptive research design was adopted for this study to answer the research questions about emotional states, interpersonal support, and work-life balance. The research also looked at how different emotional states, levels of social support, and work-life balance were related.

Respondents

The realty firm's remote workers in Pasay City were the subjects of this research. Because of the current COVID-19 pandemic issue, the researcher resorted to using a basic random sample method, in which everyone in the population is selected at random, rather than the intended stratified random sampling strategy. The odds of selecting a person to participate in a sample are uniform. Several departments contributed to the researcher's success in gathering a minimum of one hundred (100) responses.

Instruments

The following research instruments were administered by the researcher to measure the variables presented.

Work-Related Quality of Life Scale

Employees' perceptions of their own quality of life are assessed using the 23-item Work-Related Quality of Life (WRQoL) scale, which is based on six psychosocial sub-factors. Researchers, companies, and consultants all utilize the WRQoL measure to better understand and evaluate workers' quality of life on the job. A person's work experience may be broadly and simply described by the acronym QoWL, which stands for Quality of Working Life. An individual's quality of work life (QoWL) is affected by both their immediate work experience and the variables, both direct and indirect, that impact it. The policies of an organization, an employee's character traits, his or her sense of well-being, and the actual working environment all have a role in how that person rates their Quality of Working Life. According to the WRQoL handbook, the following scores indicate a high degree of psychosocial factors: The average level of psychosocial elements falls on the following scores: GWB; 22.00-30.00, HWI; 12.00-15.00, JCS; 23.00-36.00, CaW; 12.00 - 15.00, WC; 12.00-15.00, and SaW; 6.00-10.00. Low average of psychosocial variables falls on GWB; 1.00-2.00, HWI; 1.00-9.99, JCS; 1.00-19.99, CaW - 1.00-9.99, WC - 1.00-10.99, and SaW - 1.00-4.99, with GWB, HWI, JCS, CaW, WC, and SaW all falling within the range of 20.01-21.99, 10.00-11.99, and 11.00-11.99, respectively.

Interpersonal Support Evaluation List

The 40 items that make up the Interpersonal Support Evaluation List are divided into four sections. The subscales are Support that is tangible. A sense of belonging, support for self-esteem, and feedback on performance. Each statement on the item is rated according to the participants' own belief in its truth or falsehood. Any response may be marked as either "Definitely True" or "Definitely False" on a 4-point scale.

The items that are scored in reverse order are 3, 6, 9, 10, 11, 13, 14, 15, 17, 24, 25, 27, 28, 29, 30, 34, 35, 36, 39, and 40. The Appraisal Support Subscale consists of items 1, 6, 11, 17, 19, 22, 26, 30, 36, and 38. The Tangible Support Subscale consists of items 2, 9, 14, 16, 18, 23, 29, 33, 35, and 39. The Self-Esteem Support Subscale consists of items 3, 4, 8, 13, 20, 24, 28, 32, 37, and 40. The Belonging Support Subscale consists of items 5, 7, 10, 12, 15, 21, 25, 27, 31, and 34. Continuous scores are maintained.

Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale – Long Form (DASS-42)

The 42-item Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale (DASS) assesses the mental health of those who work remotely by measuring levels of stress, anxiety, and depression. Based on this metric, there are two separate areas mental stress (nervous tension and nervous energy) and physical anxiety (fear symptomatology). For the last seven days, this screening and result metric has been in use. The DASS 42 is a measuring instrument that includes 42 questions across three subscales; it takes between ten and twenty minutes to do the assessment; and it is translated into thirty-three languages. As part of a more comprehensive clinical evaluation, the DASS is most useful for pinpointing the source of emotional distress. The DASS is primarily designed to measure the intensity of the main symptoms of stress, anxiety, and depression. Researchers and therapists will find the DASS scales useful for measuring present or changing states because of their excellent internal consistency and their ability to provide meaningful discriminations in different contexts (Novopsych, 2018). Levels of depression range from normal (0–9), anxiety from 0–7, and stress from 0–14 on the DASS–42 scale. Levels of mild depression range from 10–13, anxiety from 8–9, and stress from 15–18 on the scale. Levels of moderate depression range from 14–20, anxiety from 10–14, and stress from 19–25 on the scale. Very Severe Depression is characterized by a score of 28+, Anxiety by a score of 20+, and Stress by a score of 34+. Severe Depression is measured on a 21-27 scale, Anxiety by a score of 15-19, and Stress by a score of 26.33.

Procedure

The researcher then sought suitable instruments to assess the study's variables. A work-home conflict scale was used to assess work-life balance, while the DASS-42 was utilized to measure emotional state. The authors of the instruments were notified of the acceptance of the proposed defense and asked to submit their permission. The researcher addressed a letter to the management of organizations that have recently implemented work-from-home policies to request permission to conduct the study after the authors gave their assent. The researchers in question then liaised with the director of human resources to get staff members involved after receiving consent. To guarantee the dependability of the responders, the researcher used Google Forms to create surveys and send them to a single company's email address. The statistical methodology used in this research to get the results of the data is quantitative, including measures such as mean, standard deviation, and Pearson correlation coefficient (r).

Ethical Considerations

Informed consent is obtained from all participants. An informed consent form that includes information regarding the procedures, benefits, and risks of participation, an explanation of how to obtain the research results, voluntary participation, and contact information for the researchers involved. The rationale was presented prior to the initial phase of the instrumentation, and the participants were informed of the full purpose and process of their involvement in the research. The researchers reassured the participants that all pertinent personal data they disclosed is highly regarded in accordance with the Philippines' data privacy act. Additionally, the research endeavor was founded on a statement of confidentiality and adherence to the ethical standards of research.

Results and Discussion

The section provides the data in a tabulated form which were interpreted and analyzed to answer the specific questions raised from the beginning of the study.

Table 1. *Work-life balance among the Respondents*

<i>Domains</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
General Well-being (GWB)	21.89	4.055	Average
Home-work Interface (HWI)	11.54	2.363	Average
Job and Career Satisfaction	23.34	3.633	High
Control at Work (CaW)	10.81	2.419	Average
Working Condition (WC)	11.55	2.032	Average
Stress at Work (SaW)	5.78	2.121	Average

Table 1 presents the work life balance among the respondents in terms of their general well-being, home-work interface, job and career satisfaction, control at work, working condition, and stress at work.

Based on the collected data, the respondents were found to have high job and career satisfaction. Respondents' result on getting a high score on job and career satisfaction reveals that working remotely has a sense of achievement, high self-esteem, and potential fulfillment. According to one of the respondents' testimonies during data gathering, despite the numerous zoom meetings, the frequent interruptions from family members, and the lack of distinction between work and personal life, they were able to do their jobs at home and seemed to be happier than those who continued to report physically to their usual workplace.

The work-from-home set-up has been a silver lining that made employers and employees realize that expected work output in the traditional physical office set-up can also be attained in the remote work options in their respective homes. Therefore, working from home is possible (Rhonski, 2020). Indeed, job satisfaction of remote workers during the pandemic surprisingly increased because of non-exposure to the virus, good pay, and an opportunity to have quality time with their family members. According to Collins (2021), the value we assign to our lives, and, by extension, our mastery of work-life balance should come down to how well we are able to prioritize the aspects of our lives that we enjoy most, whether they are professional or personal. This concludes that a person may attain a work-life balance by enjoying it their professional aspect or personal dimension. This is not limited to the situations where the individual spends most of his time with, but rather to the feeling they are experiencing either in personal life, with family and friends or in a professional aspect, together with their colleagues and other team members.

General well-being, home-work interface, control-at-work, working condition, and stress-at-work fall in the average level. This result shows that the remote workers have a balanced time, well spent in work and the family. They also view that the two parties are both critical, unlike to common complaints of people in the industry that they are obligated to spend majority of their waking hours complying with their workloads as much as they want to prioritize family time. As supported by the study conducted by Schall (2019), which states that employees who engage in remote work do so more frequently, which leads to greater satisfaction with their jobs. Also, Courtney (2021) shares that COVID-19 forced companies worldwide to send their employees home to work virtually, remote work had a big moment, and the transition could be overwhelming. This is the exact feeling that the respondents experience. After settling in all the access to the tools they would need to work from home, it quickly became apparent to many office-based teams that employees were not given a concrete plan of the remote set-up. The average scores of the respondents reflect that even though they feel better when working from home, they are unsatisfied with the service provided by their company and they began to understand that remote work really works but external support is a must.

In general, they are more willing to put in extra hours to compensate for the advantages they attain by having a work-from-home set up. Ravikant (2020) admits that this one of the potential benefits of remote work for employees, managers, and companies alike. When shifted to work from home, Respondents have more time to organize and control how they work in their comfort zone. Alagat (2019) approves that remote working enhanced productivity, flexibility, access to global talents, cost-saving, better working environment, and environmental impact.

In general, this research implies that remote workers often have a moderate degree of satisfaction in their job. Considering the subscale scores that fall under the average range, it may help the remote workers identify areas where they might usefully look to see if there are positive changes they could make. Such changes could result in a higher quality of working life and help them feel good about life

in general.

Table 2. *Interpersonal Support among the Respondents*

<i>Domains</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Appraisal Support	25.28	5.209	High
Tangible Support	22.53	5.321	High
Self-Esteem Support	18.80	4.383	Average
Belonging Support	21.35	4.130	High

N=100; Legend: 0 – 9.99 (Low); 10:00 – 19.99 (Average); 20.00-30.00 (High)

Table 2 presents the level of interpersonal support among the respondents in terms of appraisal support, tangible support, self-esteem support, and belonging support. The self-esteem support is the least likely domain that gained high scores.

Based on the table, respondents garnered an average level of self-esteem support. During pandemics and work-from-home setup, remote workers feel blessed because they got a chance to spend more time with their families. Aside from this, they could exercise their right not to be with the people they do not prefer to work with. Though quality time with family and working remotely with colleagues helped them boost their self-esteem, they were also conscious of working with people they perceive as difficult. In an organization, it is essential to have a healthy working environment to achieve a work-life balance. However, employees cannot hide the fact that not all organizations have a healthy working environment and healthy personality of co-workers; shifting from office set up to work from home set up helps the employees to choose what positive or negative thoughts that they will entertain while working remotely in their respective home.

Roberts (2015) shared that employees who have a high level of self-esteem will trust their thinking and judgment and are therefore likely to make better decisions. Having these qualities also enables leaders to create more effective interpersonal and work relationships, which means that they can more effectively contribute to the work environment. Aside from the situation above, the average level of self-esteem support suggests that variables that can be caused the increased self-esteem of the respondents lessened, most likely, being with their colleagues that served as their support system.

Given that many employees shifted from office work to work from home set-up during the pandemic, remote workers' physical connection with co-employees changed to virtual and online. Based on the table, appraisal support, tangible support, and belonging support fall in the high percentile group, while self-esteem support falls in the average range. The result indicates that employees who shifted to work from home during the pandemic gained emotional support that allowed them to feel valued, accepted, and understood. Employees that shifted to work from home set-up received continuous salary and financial support from their company, which is why they can provide more for their families. Also, remote workers receive a high level of emotional support, and the availability of others for social engagement is present during work from home set up.

The impressive score of the respondents in appraisal support reveals that remote workers still manage to receive and experience social support. They were able to adjust to the situation and maximize online platforms to build new networks and regaining ties with previous relationships. In the respondents' case, permanent teleworking allowed them to distance themselves from negative or non-essential work relationships while developing positive ones, predominantly with other teleworkers (Golden, 2006; Tietze and Nadin, 2011). Teleworking allowed people to avoid groups that they do not identify with and strengthen relations with those they saw as valuable and identified closely with. In effect, teleworkers could preserve positive social relationships with selected co-workers on their terms and avoid the negative aspects of office life they did not like. (Collins, Hislop, and Cartwright, 2016).

As first-time remote workers during the pandemic, respondents expressed their gratitude for still being employed despite the enormous economic dropdown. Yeoh & Wen (2020) explained that businesses have yet to recover from the financial impact brought by the pandemic and that they are still struggling to cope with the turbulence. Respondents are also happy that the company is exerting effort to support them, despite the lack of sources extended to them like continuous pay, the weekly meetings with their teams and the material aid that the company provided to support their employees during pandemic.

Table 3. *The emotional States among the Respondents*

<i>Domains</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Depression	7.82	7.288	Normal
Anxiety	8.01	5.872	Mild
Stress	10.75	6.616	Normal

Table 3 shows the level of emotional states among the respondents in terms of depression, anxiety, and stress. Based on the table above, depression and stress fall along the normal range, indicating that respondents as remote workers during the pandemic have no evidence of depression and stress. Their anxiety level indicates a mild manifestation of the said variable.

The result of the anxiety domain under the emotional states variable falls in the mild range which means respondents shows autonomic arousal, skeletal muscle effects, situational anxiety, and subjective experience of anxious affect. According to the study of Garner (2020), people seem to feel more alone without the necessary support they need. The sudden lack of physical connection can leave

workers feeling that they have nowhere to turn to when they feel stressed or anxious. According to Healy (2017), the reason why remote workers experience anxiety during work from home setup is that it is relatively easy to trust someone you have spent years sharing a physical space with while it is much harder to trust a digital avatar. Though virtual communication somehow resolves this issue, it does not bring the authentic feeling of being surrounded by the people the respondents used to be with. Some of them are also acquainted with the technology. However, some respondents shared that they still struggle to utilize such technology, especially when their gadgets are not high-end, and that it fluctuates after prolonged use. The adjustment to technology is one of the most leading causes of anxiety to the respondents. Some of them are fonder of manual processes and had a hard time discovering the power of technology especially that this was the first time they shifted to work from home set up.

We Work Remotely (2020) also published that loneliness and isolation of remote working also cause anxiety. Single respondents just manage to communicate conversation when they are at their workplace, that they miss the healthy noise when they are surrounded by their co-workers. The social aspect of chatting and venting about work and life is absent when they work remotely. This camaraderie does not translate the same way over remote set-up. Boundary issues also lead to working from home, where anxiety takes on many forms, including pressure to hustle 24/7. Because communication lands on social media, respondents feel social media toxicity and find no time to disconnect and unplug; therefore, they are at risk of burning out.

Remote workers normal interpretation on their Depression and Stress show that employees who shifted to work from home set-up during a pandemic can manage their depression and stress and that they can achieve work-life balance at the same time. According to the study of Virtanen (2020), remote working can increase job satisfaction since it enables them to be more effective workers. Factors that may lead to depressive and stressful events are manageable at home. It also magnifies the importance of family and how people feel when their significant others surround them.

Working from home offers several benefits, including a reduction in stress, more time for interests and hobbies, and better personal connections, so it's no surprise that remote workers are generally happier and more loyal employees. The opportunity to design a home office that is both functional and pleasant for employees in 2020 is a perk offered by the International Labor Organization. Considering the current pandemic crisis, people who are able to work remotely may find it easier to manage their mental states, including melancholy and stress, and make healthier decisions.

Table 4. Relationship between the Appraisal Support Domain of Interpersonal Support and Work-life balance among the Respondents

Domains of Quality of Work Life	r	p-value	Interpretation	Decision	Conclusion
General Well-being	.202*	.044	Positive weak relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Home-work Interface	.089	.377	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Job and Career Satisfaction	.112	.268	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Control at Work	.056	.583	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Working Condition	.181	.072	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Stress at Work	.146	.146	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant

**Correlation significance at 0.01 (2-tailed)

*Correlation significance at 0.05 (2-tailed)

Coefficient of correlation: ± 1.00 (Perfect relationship); ± 0.76 to ± 0.99 (Very strong relationship); ± 0.51 to ± 0.75 (Strong relationship); ± 0.26 to ± 0.50 (Moderate relationship); ± 0.11 to ± 0.25 (Weak relationship); ± 0.01 to ± 0.10 (Very weak relationship); and 0.00 (No relationship)

Table 4 presents the relationship between the appraisal support domain and work-life balance among the respondents. It could be gleaned that appraisal support and general well-being have a positive, very weak relationship and found to be significantly correlated. This result leads to the decision of rejecting the null hypothesis. The significant relationship between general well-being and appraisal support could be perceived that respondent's well-being are attributed to the factors relative to appraisal. Heartwarming appraisals contribute to the well-being of the respondents. According to Jarden et al. (2018), the construct of respondents' well-being is described as rich and multifaceted, with critical features scaffolding individual, team, and organizational levels, inclusive of factors that transcend work (the role), workers (the individuals and teams), and workplaces (organizations). It could be gleaned that the support from their managers is highly appreciated even they are distant and while working from home. Haley et al. (2004) also view appraisals as a method

in psychosocial intervention. This intervention was found to be effective during pre- pandemic to assist coping, much more efficient in today's time where the world is experiencing a global pandemic. The company where the respondents are employed implemented a Power Monday. Every Mondays, the manager spends a thirty-minute to one-hour kamustahan. Respondents illustrate how they feel empowered every time they share their life disregarding office concerns. They become more familiar with the life of each other, and unconsciously, such activity builds a positive attitude towards their team members.

As intrinsically social creatures, most human beings find their most significant source of happiness and satisfaction in relationships with other people. Through this activity, respondents can create, transmit, and interpret messages while improving their interpersonal communication and quality of life. However, other communication contexts such as small group communication, organizational communication, and even mass communication can also be associated with personal well-being (Segrin, 2014).

The no significant relationship between appraisal support and the other domains such as home-work interface, job and career satisfaction, control-at-work, working condition, and home-work interface indicates that the availability of someone to talk to about one's problems has nothing to do with having a measure of control over when, where, and how remote workers work during a pandemic. In a survey made by Half in 2020, 60 per cent of employees report an improved work-life balance during the pandemic, despite enjoying extra time with family and not dealing with commuting and other downsides of in-office work. Employees who shifted to work from home set up during the pandemic found satisfaction working at home as they can work while having time with their families. Also, based on the study made by Almeida in 2019, social support can, however, be more emotional in the engaging configuration of active emotions with other members, both inside and outside the organization. It can also have an instrumental configuration, through the more or less tangible manner of these interactions that facilitate results, work execution, financial assistance, and other facilitated aids or assets. This also reveals that other than the appraisal support, respondents matter other strengths as their support system.

Table 5. *Relationship between the Tangible Support Domain of Interpersonal Support and Work-life Balance among the Respondents*

Domains of Quality of Work Life	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	Interpretation	Decision	Conclusion
General Well-being	.159	.155	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Home-work Interface	.082	.416	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Job and Career Satisfaction	.057	.570	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Control at Work	.100	.324	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Working Condition	.019	.853	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Stress at Work	.222*	.027	Positive weak relationship	Reject Ho	Significant

**Correlation significance at 0.01 (2-tailed)
*Correlation significance at 0.05 (2-tailed)

Table 5 presents the relationship between the tangible support domain and work-life balance among the respondents. Based on the data presented respondents' tangible support and stress at work showed a significant relationship, therefore, null hypothesis is rejected. In contrast, tangible support more likely corresponds to the stress level among employees, based on the realized significance. This claim is supported by Gallup (2020), who suggested that millennials who are working remotely say they feel just as much happiness and enjoyment as non-remote millennials; they are more liable to report experiencing anxiety, loneliness, stress, sadness, and worry.

The tangible support domain pertains to physical assets like cash, inventory, vehicles, equipment, buildings, and investments. The data on this study has been gathered in the middle of the pandemic where people are restricted to go outside without their local government unit's approval to attend to essential matters. During this time, respondents realized that they might have cars, but it is not safe to go outside; therefore, their vehicle is no use. Similarly, they may have plenty of cash, but no amount can suffice the safety and security they need in these trying times. They may have other investments, like insurance, but they wish not to use them because it could mean losing a loved one. Therefore, tangible support has nothing to do with their general well-being, home-work interface, job and career satisfaction, control at work, working conditions and Stress at Work which all have an insignificant relationship with tangible support, respondents feel nothing is better than being surrounded by their family and loved ones.

The degree to which respondents' organization understands and tries to help them with pressures outside of work is not related to their tangible or physical assets. When respondents struggle with internet connectivity, they see it as something that neither they nor their company can control. In addition, though respondents are compensated, they shared that they are willing to prioritize their careers if they are required to report physically. As home-work interface can be achieved when there is a feeling of fulfilment in both inside and outside paid work, this domain of work-life balance does not concern the hygienic factors of motivation. Likewise, working conditions

as a domain is insignificant to tangible support, highlighting the respondents' immeasurable love for their family and their presence amid the pandemic. While Filipinos are universally aware of the importance of staying healthy, they saw that their behaviors are largely influenced by fears and worries, including concern fulfillment family and feeling financially unprepared for illnesses (Heightened Concerns about Family and Finances Drive Filipinos'

Table 6. *Relationship between the Self Esteem Support Domain of Interpersonal Support and Work-life balance among the Respondents*

Domains of Quality of Work Life	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	Interpretation	Decision	Conclusion
General Well-being	.279**	.005	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Home-work Interface	.004	.971	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Job and Career Satisfaction	.089	.380	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Control at Work	.122	.226	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Working Condition	.017	.867	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Stress at Work	.009	.926	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant

**Correlation significance at 0.01 (2-tailed)

*Correlation significance at 0.05 (2-tailed)

Table 6 presents the relationship between the self-esteem support domain and work-life balance among the respondents. Based on the table above, respondents' self-esteem support and general well-being showed significant relationship, rejecting the null hypothesis. General well-being is the result of a dynamic balance between various aspects of the employees. It automatically flows into their lives, when the spiritual, cognitive, emotional, physical, and behavioral parts of our lives are integrated, balanced and working well. With this, Galanakis (2016) found that self-esteem may likely be affected by stress. Researchers suggest that this interaction occurs at different levels (i.e., psychological, personal, and professional). They emphasized the importance of stress management techniques to improve self-esteem.

Parallel to this, Stahl (2020) shared that as a preventative measure, employees should live a life like that they are in the office. First, it is critical is to find a balance in the workspace at home. Begin by implementing office hours, silencing notifications, and activating an out-of-office response outside of predetermined time blocks. This way, no matter how remote employees are out running an errand or winding down from the day on the couch, both managers and clients know that their office is closed for business. If possible, create a block of hours that they can consistently work within, and be sure to communicate this upfront with staff and customers to avert any surprises. Stahl (2020) suggested that when someone tries to push back and schedule a late-night meeting, remote employees should not be afraid to stand in their values, like respectfully refusing to commit outside office hours. Researcher observed that remote worker's general well-being is relevant to the self-esteem support that they get from the company and their colleagues, one of the respondents shared that the weekly meeting that they have every Monday helped them create wellness space to their human body. Sharing experiences, achievements and life lessons to your colleagues and assuring everyone in the team that they have someone on their back can really boost morale and self-esteem of remote workers regardless of if it is virtual or online.

Data showed no significant relationship between the respondents' self-esteem to home-work interface, job and career satisfaction, control at work, working condition, and stress at work. Although Yang, H.C. et al. (2016) found that job stress has a significantly negative effect on job satisfaction and self-esteem, it was shown that self-esteem has a partially mediating effect, and turnover experience had a moderating effect. Research suggests that it is crucial to shed new light on the roles of self-esteem among determinants of job satisfaction. The tangible sources produced home-work interface have nothing to do with the self-esteem of the respondents. The way the respondents value and perceive themselves is insignificant. Their opinions and beliefs about themselves are not affected nor can be seen as a relative by the hygienic factors like compensation. Dolan & S. (2021) shared that people may either view the positive or negative about themselves. Self-esteem seems to be associated with stressors that have to do with emotion. Low self-esteem is sometimes called low self-worth. It is perhaps due to the sufferings brought by the COVID-19 crisis.

Table 7 presents the relationship between the belonging support domain and work-life balance among the respondents. Based on the data presented, there is a significant relationship between respondents' belonging support and work-life balance, making the null hypothesis rejected. The general well-being of employees relates to all aspects of their working life, from the quality and safety of their physical environment, to how they feel about their work, their working environment, the climate at work and work organization. All these are to make sure workers are safe, healthy, satisfied and engaged at work.

Table 7. Relationship between the Belonging Support Domain of Interpersonal Support and Work-life balance among the Respondents

Domains of Quality of Work Life	r	p-value	Interpretation	Decision	Conclusion
General Well-being	.219*	.029	Positive weak relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Home-work Interface	.086	.395	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Job and Career Satisfaction	.153	.129	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Control at Work	.127	.208	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Working Condition	.039	.697	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Stress at Work	.086	.394	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant

**Correlation significance at 0.01 (2-tailed)

*Correlation significance at 0.05 (2-tailed)

Morin (2020) shared that the absence of distress does not necessarily indicate a person has high psychological well-being. High psychological well-being is about feeling happy and doing well. People with high psychological well-being report feeling capable, happy, well-supported, and satisfied with life. That is why respondents, based on the results on the table above, shared that connection with other people is essential to promote their well-being. It is a need that can be gratified by being with others. To develop general well-being, the need for belongingness should not be left behind. Likewise, to foster it, these two constructs need one another. For instance, they foster positive relationships, exhibit kindness through helping, express gratitude, and practice mindfulness. In line with the importance of belonging support, Moeller et al., (2020) suggested a strong relationship between perceived rejection and mental health problems. Researchers suggest that intervention efforts could target individuals who are experiencing feelings of rejection. Then these individuals can be subjected to additional psychological intervention to support well-being.

Data shows no significant relationship between the respondents' belonging support to home-work interface, job and career satisfaction, control at work, working condition, and stress at work. Belongingness according to Maslow, as cited by Cherry (2021), refers to a human emotional need to affiliate with and be accepted by members of a group. For instance, it may refer to the need to belong to a peer group at school, be accepted by co-workers, be part of an athletic team, or be part of a religious group. The need to belong is what drives people to seek out secure, lifetime connections with other people.

For the respondents, their work is a separate entity from their support system that makes them feel they belonged. Likewise, it could be perceived that they can feel belongingness even in the absence or lack of support from their management outside their comfort zone. Panchal et al. (2021) reported that the COVID-19 pandemic and the resulting economic recession have negatively affected many people's mental health and created new barriers for people already with mental illness and substance use disorders. Because of this, the presence and support of family, being the fundamental root of every being, is vital to overcome the challenges predetermined by the situation. Also, Parker-Griffin (2020) shared that 48% of their respondents reported that they are currently doing their jobs remotely based on the workforce survey. For the companies who could easily transition their staff to remote work, it has been the ideal situation for many employees. There is a 44% of remote employees who indicated that they are happier to have their job now than they were before the outbreak. In addition, there seems to be an overwhelming sentiment that management and leadership teams are on the right track. The 88% of remote workers said they are confident that their organization's leadership is making the right business decisions to manage through the current environment. The respondents of this study shared the same perception in the conducted survey. They attribute their high job and career satisfaction with the current remote work set-up because they feel empowered to choose their schedules and priorities in life. However, it has nothing to do with their sense of belongingness, as they perceived that their belonging support is a separate entity from their job and career satisfaction and the rest of the domains of interpersonal support that has no significant relationship with belonging support, and the reason and how they achieve both are not linked to each other. In Abraham Maslow's hierarchy of needs, belongingness is part of one of his significant needs that motivate human behavior. The hierarchy is usually portrayed as a pyramid, with more basic needs at the base and more complex needs near the peak. However, respondents seem not to mind this as it is found not linked in their control at remote work. It also seems like respondents have a clear definition of boundaries between their work and home spheres.

Respondents are psychologically detached from work, especially when they are at home satisfying their sense of belonging. In a survey conducted by CNBC and SurveyMonkey, over half of all employees (54%) say it has gotten "somewhat harder" or "much harder" to do their job effectively compared to the results before the pandemic. The mandate of remote work, along with limited ability to travel and meet in person, has forced companies to be creative and utilize new technologies to be productive. This could be an example of the implications and effects of instant change. Organizations have had to react quickly, often changing their operations, business models, and customer service to meet newly imposed government regulations without implementing effective change management strategies. In totality, this can impact the job difficulty (or perceived difficulty) level for workers (Parker-Griffin, 2020). Though stress

and belongingness are both psychological constructs, respondents reveal that in this study, they are not related to each other and their working conditions. A sense of belonging involves more than simply being acquainted with other people. It is centered on gaining acceptance, attention, and support from members of the group and providing the same attention to other members (Cherry, 2021). Respondents' stress level is not linked to their sense of belonging. Though they express focus on the similarities and connection with other people, they do not think that the latter's non-acceptance could be problematic and stressful. They also shared that maybe because of the set parameters of the virus responsible for the pandemic, their mindset is to be distant physically but not emotionally to other people. That has been helpful to the respondents because they can feel connected even without being physically available for others.

Table 8. Relationship between Depression and Quality of Work-life Balance among the Respondents

Domains of Quality of Work Life	r	p-value	Interpretation	Decision	Conclusion
General Well-being	-.541**	.000	Negative strong relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Homework interface	-.281*	.005	Negative moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Job and Career Satisfaction	-.344**	.000	Negative Moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Control at Work	-.223*	.026	Negative weak relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Working Condition	-.374**	.000	Negative moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Stress at Work	-.235**	.019	Negative weak relationship	Reject Ho	Significant

**Correlation significance at 0.01 (2-tailed)

*Correlation significance at 0.05 (2-tailed)

General well-being has the highest negative strong relationship with Depression among all domains of work life balance, a lower level of depression brings an increase in general well-being. Courtney (2021) shared that many remote jobs also come with flexible schedules, which means that workers can start and end their day as they choose if their work is complete and leads to solid outcomes. This opportunity has been helping the respondents to develop well-being; that is why it could be cited that from Table 3, they have an average level of depression. It could also be anticipated that once their well-being becomes more adjusted with the current situation, their depression level shall lower down. Some respondents shared that they feel secured working at home and cannot experience the terrible transportation of Metro Manila, also the researcher observed that it is with great opportunity for remote workers to stay at home and protect their loved ones from the current pandemic that the world is suffering. The chance to have a flexible schedule and output-based requirements made the respondents feel less miserable. Since they were required to work from home, they save much time, energy, and finances. They do not have to experience heavy daily traffic where they have many horror stories to tell. They also have the freedom to work without getting dressed in corporate attire and have the available time to include leisure while working.

Research cited by Courtney (2021) shows that commuting 10 miles to work each day is associated with health issues like higher cholesterol, elevated blood sugar, and an increased risk of depression. Ditching the commute helps the respondents support their mental and physical health. The time savings allowed them to focus on priorities outside of work, like getting extra sleep in the morning, spending more time with family, getting in a workout, or eating a healthy breakfast. This is the same reason why depression is significantly related to control at work. This control over the work schedule can be invaluable when attending to the needs of personal life. Also, Scott (2020) discussed that many people think maintaining a work-life balance is primarily based on diminishing activities from one's schedule. Indeed, setting priorities, simplifying schedules, and learning time management techniques are significant parts of work-life balance.

Homework interface, job satisfaction, control at work, working conditions and stress at work are also have moderate to weak significant relationship with depression. Microsoft (2021) revealed that workers are happier working from home and feel more pressure to be always available to bosses. The COVID-19 pandemic has seen a dramatic shift to remote working over the past year, with many people working from home. This new way of working has allowed workers to live life differently. Fifty-five percent now use their lunch break to focus on their personal lives, and 56% reported an increase in their happiness levels working from home. However, many employees said that they are being stretched further in the work they need to deliver. Nearly one in three (30%) reported an increase in their hours while working from home, and more than half (53%) feel they must always be available.

The respondents of the current study, as remote employees have boundaries. As one of the respondents mentioned they gladly comply even during work hours because of the sense of trust that their employers have given them to accomplish their tasks. They claimed that

they want to return the favor to the company when they were allowed to run some personal errands and tasks by working remotely. They feel that they can control their stressors and commit to stress management which eventually increases positive coping mechanisms necessary in reaching a more balanced life and at the same time being able to manage daily hassles.

Table 9. *Relationship between Anxiety and Work-life balance among the Respondents*

Domains of Quality of Work Life	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	Interpretation	Decision	Conclusion
General Well-being	-.321**	.001	Negative moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Home-work Interface	-.204**	.047	Negative weak relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Job and Career Satisfaction	-.255*	.010	Negative weak relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Control at Work	-.098	.332	Negative very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not significant
Working Condition	-.311**	.002	Negative Moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Stress at Work	-.349	.000	Negative moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant

**Correlation significance at 0.01 (2-tailed)

*Correlation significance at 0.05 (2-tailed)

Table 9 revealed the relationship between anxiety and work life balance among the respondents. Based on the data presented, there is significant relationship between respondents' anxiety and general well-being, home-work interface, job and career satisfaction, and working condition, which led to the decision to reject the null hypothesis.

The significant relationships between respondents' anxiety and work-life balance means that they are interconnected. Bakhshi, et.al. (2018) suggest that anxiety among employees could be lessened significantly by improving work quality. They added that implementing uniform incentive programs and improving the work environment in physical and mental well-being may increase their quality of work life.

Respondents were glad to receive their compensation religiously even though there was no salary increase implemented, and bonuses were canceled.

Among the domains of emotional states, it could be seen that respondents experience a mild level of anxiety. Scott (2020) suggests that to relieve anxiety, gratifications that can bring life satisfaction should be pursued. She emphasized that gratifications are hobbies that utilize individual strengths and creativity just the right way and eventually bring fulfillment. GitLab (2020) stated that people should not celebrate long hours of work. According to them, there is individual freedom, and there is peer pressure. Companies should take much care that there is no peer pressure to work long hours. Respondents of the study mentioned during data gathering that this pandemic was the only reason that their Company shifted to working remotely and the experience of being demanded to submit outputs even after working hours puts pressure and uncomfortable feeling towards remote workers.

As the results suggest, a decrease in anxiety level is an increase in the domains of work-life balance. Respondents are impressed with how the company tries to connect with them and adapt to the new norms predetermined by the pandemic. However, the remote set-up made them experience that some managers are insensitive with how they relay positive remarks. There is a fine line between acknowledging someone in public for going above and beyond to help out in a situation and sending a message that work should always exceed personal life. Burnout rarely happens all at once. Instead, it typically takes one by surprise, eventually coming to a head after days, weeks, or months of overwork suffering. While working one additional hour to move a given project forward is likely not debilitating when viewed in a vacuum, it can trigger a revised baseline where respondents must continue to overwork to maintain the new status quo. Sooner or later, it becomes toxic when managers fail to recognize that a given sprint should not reset the baseline of what is achievable on an ongoing, sustained basis. It becomes devastating when they do not feel safe bringing this up to their managers in a private dialogue. Particularly in their company, where results are valued above all, managers should be careful not to assume that results garnered in each period of overwork are the new norm. Respondents complain that this places them in an unfair scenario where they feel pressured to perpetually overwork to meet expectations, especially when they feel that they have to respond 24/7. Because of this, rest and peace and mind are sometimes a luxury of being a remote worker with insistent management.

On the other hand, respondents' anxiety and control at work show no significant relationship. This means that even if other quality of work life factors increases along with anxiety, employees do not necessarily seek control at work. However, as Bakshi et al. (2018) suggested, it is essential to implement, monitor, and assess programs for employees. This approach, according to the researchers, may

include the exclusion of the related barriers and prevention of mental disorders such as anxiety to promote quality work life.

Table 10. *Relationship between Stress and Work-life balance among the Respondents*

Domains of Quality of Work Life	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	Interpretation	Decision	Conclusion
General Well-being	-.373**	.000	Negative Moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Home-work Interface	-.195	.051	Negative weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Job and Career Satisfaction	-.227*	.023	Negative weak relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Control at Work	-.130	.196	Negative very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Working Condition	-.261**	.009	Negative Moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Stress at Work	-.380**	.000	Negative Moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant

**Correlation significance at 0.01 (2-tailed)

*Correlation significance at 0.05 (2-tailed)

Table 10 presents the relationship between stress and work-life balance among the respondents. Based on the data above, there is a significant relationship between respondents' stress and their general well-being, job and career satisfaction, working condition, and stress at work. This means that as the stress of workers increases, it is likely that they are also in need of quality work life at some aspects of their work. The current research shows different results compared to other studies. The study of Aruldos et al. (2020) suggested quality of work life is negatively related to job stress but positively related to job satisfaction and positively related to job commitment.

Scott (2021) reported that 41% of employees who more often worked from home vs. on-site considered themselves highly stressed, compared to 25% of those who worked only on-site, while 42% of those who work from home report frequent night waking, while only 29% of office workers reported the same. Employees who work from home may experience more of a blur when it comes to work and personal life boundaries, especially with smart devices. In addition, respondents struggle more with the concept of unplugging and ending their workday compared to those who work in an office setting.

Although the current research data shows no significant relationship between respondents' stress to home-work interface and control at work, it is vital to track the implications of stress to quality of work life. Aruldos et.al. (2020) reported that their study was limited due to extraneous variables such as social desirability bias and common method bias among respondents. They claimed that knowing these implications may likely influence human resource managers' and employers' practice in work organizations in achieving organizational effectiveness.

Table 11. *Relationship Between Depression and Interpersonal Support among the Respondents*

Domains of Interpersonal Support	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	Interpretation	Decision	Conclusion
Appraisal Support	-.543**	.000	Negative strong relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Tangible Support	-.431**	.000	Negative moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Self-Esteem Support	-.504**	.000	Negative moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Belonging Support	-.411**	.000	Negative moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant

**Correlation significance at 0.01 (2-tailed)

*Correlation significance at 0.05 (2-tailed)

As revealed on Table 11, the significant relationship between depression to interpersonal support has strong negative relationship to appraisal support which means that the high appraisal supports the remote employees receive from their organization lowered their

depression. The current data also illustrate the emotional impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the emotional state of workers. Alnazy et.al. (2021) supported this result, who suggested that the COVID-19 pandemic has affected healthcare workers' mental health. Researchers examined workers' social support from friends and families during the pandemic. They found out that these workers demonstrated an increased need for social support to adjust to psychological distress. Researchers suggest that healthcare organizations should identify early signs of psychological distress by promoting early assessment to address social support policy.

Data also showed moderate to strong negative relationships between the rest of the domains of interpersonal support and depression which is a very clear indication that to alleviate depression, the remote workers' interpersonal support should be maintained. They should be appraised even without committing to overtime, paid to compensate for their complex works, boosted to increase their value, and heard to develop a sense of belongingness. The Medical City Clinic (2020) shares that unreliable internet connection is the primary concern of remote employees in their survey. These tangible needs are being shouldered by the respondents of this study which payment concerns them and the quality of the service provider. For an employee of a company that relies heavily on the internet and technology, the connectivity in the Philippines has a huge negative impact on the work performance of the remote workers. However, this also made respondents think of ways to cope with the said conditions as they learned to accept that it is something beyond their control.

The sense of belongingness felt by the remote workers is also essential to decrease their stress. However, two to five respondents shared that communication is frustrating when a co-worker is unresponsive. It is not easy to get direct answers if they do not respond quickly via digital channels. They cannot resolve problems that resulted from delays. Nevertheless, work-from-home is the most significant advantage for them since they do not have to waste their valuable time commuting, which they find incredibly stressful and depressing.

Table 12. *Relationship Between Anxiety and Interpersonal Support among the Respondents*

Domains of Interpersonal Support	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	Interpretation	Decision	Conclusion
Appraisal Support	- .433**	.000	Negative moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Tangible Support	- .370**	.001	Negative moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Self-Esteem Support	- .290**	.003	Negative moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Belonging Support	- .339**	.001	Negative moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant

**Correlation significance at 0.01 (2-tailed)

*Correlation significance at 0.05 (2-tailed)

Table 12 presents the relationship between anxiety and interpersonal support among the respondents. Based on the data presented, there is a significant relationship between respondents' anxiety and all the four domains of interpersonal support such as appraisal support, tangible support, self-esteem support, and belonging support; leading to the decision to reject the null hypothesis. One respondent shared that he feels like he is working for more than the required 8 hours at home because he tends to entertain emails from his boss and co-workers outside his working hours. For a while, this set-up was okay, but now it is making him more stressed about work. Like him, respondents agree that they are less likely to perform when they are anxious about work. In addition, respondents' cause of anxiety can affect their relational needs.

The Medical City Clinic (2020) stated that when the remote workers' encounters are not adequately dealt with, all of the significant work-from-home challenges lead to stress, anxiety, and ultimately a decline in mental health. Moreover, while so many employees have developed a way to cope with stress in the traditional office setting, dealing with the job stresses right at home can be a completely different scenario.

The significant relationships between anxiety and the other domains interpersonal support such as tangible support, self-esteem support, and belonging support depicted negative moderate correlation which indicated that the increase relational support lessens their anxiety level. These findings are relevant nowadays, especially to those individuals greatly affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. Kandeđer,

A. et.al. (2020) suggested perceived social support could increase the resilience of individuals on anxiety. They added that, as the prevalence of anxiety symptoms increases, their perceived social support likely decreases.

For the work-from-home set-up be more beneficial, specific type of work schedule intended for employees who are working remotely in their homes should be determined. It functions the same way as other work schedules for employees working in the office or actual workplace, but it has some minor distinctions. A remote worker should determine a specific time schedule and avoid distractions such TV or other gadgets at home, or even family members. Take steps to eliminate common distractions by advising family members about

being unavailable for certain spans of time each day and have a set workspace with a door which can be closed during the defined work schedule. It is important to plan carefully the custom-build schedule and then to stick with it, but allowing some flexibility should there be a need to deviate from it. This way, remote workers will be able to minimize, if not to eliminate the anxiety in their work.

Table 13. *Relationship Between the Stress and Interpersonal Support among the Respondents*

Domains of Interpersonal Support	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	Interpretation	Decision	Conclusion
Appraisal Support	- .388**	.000	Negative moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Tangible Support	- .362**	.000	Negative moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Self-Esteem Support	- .328**	.001	Negative moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
Belonging Support	- .288**	.004	Negative moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant

**Correlation significance at 0.01 (2-tailed)

*Correlation significance at 0.05 (2-tailed)

Table 13 presents the relationship between stress and interpersonal support among the respondents. Based on the data presented, there is a significant relationship between respondents' stress level and all the four domains of interpersonal support such as appraisal support, tangible support, self-esteem support, and belonging support; leading to the decision to reject the null hypothesis. Among the domains of interpersonal support, appraisal support revealed has the highest correlation with stress. The negative moderate relationship indicates that the increased appraisal support received by the remote workers decreased their stress level. Based on the researcher's observation help and support provided by one's manager decreases the probability of being stressed at work, while receiving help and support from co-workers is likely to increase the probability of job stress occurrence. Similarly, maintaining cooperation and getting along well with colleagues decrease the probability of experiencing stress, confirming the positive and gratifying features of contact with co-workers especially during this pandemic that social support was cut off temporarily.

This result is supported by the study of Nappo (2020) when he suggested that job stress is associated with difficulties managing solid relationships with family members, on and outside of the job, which can be considered valuable resources. According to the researcher, these relationships help manage workplace stressors, such as high demands and low control. The researcher realized that in his study, remote workers need a program that would support their needs. For instance, counseling is psychological support that can inhibit stress. As the workload increases their productivity and makes them feel job security, it can be stressful at times. Respondents need guidance on how to deal with and combat stress alongside the challenges brought about by the pandemic.

Stahl (2020) stressed that burnout is known to cause a series of physical and mental conditions: high blood pressure, heart disease, obesity, a weakened immune system, anxiety, depression, cognitive decline, Alzheimer's disease, and even death. With remote work, which socially isolates respondents, there is an added component to consider: loneliness. Research demonstrates that while obesity reduces longevity by 20%, drinking by 30%, and smoking by 50%, loneliness takes the cake, reducing life expectancy by a whopping 70%. It is safe to say that practicing self-awareness and establishing a healthy work-from-home lifestyle could be what keeps people safe for the long term.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study presented, the following conclusions were drawn: There is no significant relationship between work-life balance and interpersonal support among remote workers. Second, there is a significant relationship between work-life balance and emotional states among remote workers. Lastly, there is a significant relationship between interpersonal support and emotional states among remote workers.

The researchers recommend that the proposed remote worker's productivity program be implemented to address the issues identified in the study. Also, those remote workers further develop their interpersonal skills to attain work-life balance and good emotional states. In addition, the company is considering other programs that will develop the interpersonal skills of the respondents amid the pandemic. Also, the company explores other underlying factors of work-life balance, and lastly, future studies will be conducted exploring other underlying factors in work-life balance, interpersonal support, and emotional states among employees in other fields of work.

References

Alnazy, E., et al (2021). Anxiety, depression, stress, fear and social support during COVID-19 pandemic among Jordanian healthcare

workers, from <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0247679>

Aruldoss, A., et al (2020). The relationship between quality of work life and work-life- balance mediating role of job stress, job satisfaction and job commitment: evidence from India. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/JAMR-05-2020-0082/full/htm>

Bakhshi, E., et al (2018). Associations of the Quality of Work Life and Depression, Anxiety, and Stress in the Employees of Healthcare Systems, from https://psj.mums.ac.ir/article_11176_86e1aaf320da9d53623598413b18d00a

Cherry, K. (2021). What Is a Sense of Belonging? Verywell Mind. <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-the-need-to-belong-2795393>

Courtney, E. (2021, April 12). The Benefits of Working From Home: Why The Pandemic Isn't the Only Reason to Work Remotely. FlexJobs Job Search Tips and Blog. <https://www.flexjobs.com/blog/post/benefits-of-remote-work/>

Dolan, S. L., & S., S. G. (2021, January 10). Covid-19, Stress, Self-Esteem, Values, and Psychological Well-being: How to Assess Risks of Becoming Depressed, Anxious, or Suicidal? The European Business Review. <https://www.europeanbusinessreview.com/covid-19-stress-self-esteem-values-and-psychological-well-being-how-to-assess-risks-of-becoming-depressed-anxious-or-suicidal/>

Galanakis, M. J., et al (2016). A Literature Review on the Connection between Stress and Self-Esteem. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/303290862_A_Literature_Review_on_the_Connection_between_Stress_and_Self-Esteem/citations

GitLab. (2020). Combating burnout, isolation, and anxiety in the remote workplace. Retrieved May 30, 2021, from <https://about.gitlab.com/company/culture/all-remote/mental-health/>

Haar, J. M., et al (2014). Outcomes of Work-Life Balance on Job Satisfaction, Life Satisfaction and Mental Health: A Study across Seven Cultures. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/265254448_Outcomes_of_Work-Life_Balance_on_Job_Satisfaction_Life_Satisfaction_and_Mental_Health_A_Study_across_Seven_Cultures

Haley, W. E., Gitlin, L. N., Wisniewski, S. R., Mahoney, D. F., Coon, D. W., Winter, L., Corcoran, M., Schinfeld, S., & Ory, M. (2004). Well-being, appraisal, and coping in African-American and Caucasian dementia caregivers: findings from the REACH study. *Aging & Mental Health*, 8(4), 316–329. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13607860410001728998>

Heightened concerns about family and finances drive Filipinos' decisions about health and critical illness – Manulife. (2020). Insurance Site. <https://www.manulife.com.ph/en/individual/about-us/newsroom/latest-news/2020-health-study.html>

Jarden, R. J., Sandham, M., Siegert, R. J., & Koziol-McLain, J. (2018). Quality appraisal of workers' wellbeing measures: a systematic review protocol. *Systematic Reviews*, 7(1), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-018-0905-4>

Josling, M. (2015). Belongingness, Work Engagement, Stress and Job Satisfaction in a Healthcare Setting, from https://esource.dbs.ie/bitstream/handle/10788/2809/ba_josling_megan_2015.pdf?sequence=1

Kandeğer, A., et al (2020). Evaluation of the relationship between perceived social support, coping strategies, anxiety, and depression symptoms among hospitalized COVID-19 patients <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/0091217420982085>

Microsoft. (2021, February 15). Research reveals how we really feel about working from home. Microsoft News Centre UK. <https://news.microsoft.com/en-gb/2021/02/15/research-reveals-how-we-really-feel-about-working-from-home/>

Moeller, R. W., et al (2020). Emotional Intelligence, Belongingness, and Mental Health in College Students <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00093/full>

Morin, A. (2020). Simple Ways to Improve Your Psychological Well-Being. Verywell Mind. <https://www.verywellmind.com/improve-psychological-well-being-4177330>

Nappo, N. (2020). Job stress and interpersonal relationships cross country evidence from the EU15: a correlation analysis, from <https://bmcpublichealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12889-020-09253-9>

Nesta, (2021). Unprecedented Times: Taking actions during COVID-19. nesta.org.uk/feature/unprecedented-times/

Oliver Wyman. (n.d.). Employee Concerns about COVID-19. Retrieved May 29, 2021, from <https://www.mmc.com/insights/publications/2020/march/employee-concerns-about-covid-19.html>

Panchal, N., Kamal, R., Cox, C., & Garfield, R. (2021, April 14). The Implications of COVID-19 for Mental Health and Substance Use. KFF. <https://www.kff.org/coronavirus-covid-19/issue-brief/the-implications-of-covid-19-for-mental-health-and-substance-use/>

- Parker-Griffin, P. (2020, May 27). How the Pandemic Has Impacted Employee Satisfaction. BioSpace. <https://www.biospace.com/article/how-the-pandemic-has-affected-employee-satisfaction/>
- Quinn, B. A. (2020, April 20). COVID-19 and Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs: How Is Our Motivation Changing? GoodTherapy.Org Therapy Blog. <https://www.goodtherapy.org/blog/covid19-maslows-hierarchy-of-needs-how-is-our-motivation-changing-0420204>
- Ravikant, (2020). 11 Essential Tips for Managing Remote Employees. <https://getlighthouse.com/blog/10-tips-manage-remote-employees/>
- Schall, et al (2019). The relationship between remote work and Job: Satisfaction: The Mediating Roles of Perceived Autonomy, Work-Family Conflict, and Telecommuting Intensity. https://scholarworks.sjsu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=8564&context=etd_t
- Schulman, (2020). Responding to Covid-19 with Generosity, Solidarity, and Resilience. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/responding-covid-19-generosity-solidarity-res>
- Scott, E. (2020). How to Be Less Stressed With a Better Work-Life Balance. Verywell Mind. <https://www.verywellmind.com/how-to-achieve-better-work-life-balance-3145026>
- Scott, E. (2021). How to Handle the Stress of Working from Home. Verywell Mind. <https://www.verywellmind.com/the-stress-of-working-from-home-4141174>
- Segrin, C. (2014). Communication and Personal Well-Being. SpringerLink. https://link.springer.com/referenceworkentry/10.1007%2F978-94-007-0753-5_446?error=cookies_not_supported&code=5a1bc2f6-fba5-4a33-a4eb-0fd187642ea7
- Stahl, A. (2020, September 1). Work-From-Home Burnout: Causes and Cures. Forbes. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/ashleystahl/2020/09/01/work-from-home-burnout-causes-and-cures/?sh=6e15afb2b881>
- The Medical City Clinic. (2020, July 23). Maintaining Your Mental Health While Working From Home. <https://www.themedicalcityclinic.com/maintaining-your-mental-health-while-working-from-home/>
- We Work Remotely. (2020). We Work Remotely | How To Keep Your Mental Health in Check When You Work From Home. Retrieved May 29, 2021, from <https://weworkremotely.com/how-to-keep-your-mental-health-in-check-when-you-work-from-home>
- Wronski, (2020). Who is the happiest working from home, from <https://www.cnn.com/2020/05/26/who-is-happiest-working-from-home-heres-w>
- Yang, H.C., et al (2016). Effects of job stress on self-esteem, job satisfaction, and turnover intention, Journal of Transnational Management, 21:1, 29-39, DOI: 10.1080/15475778.2016.1120613
- Yeoh, L., & Wen, P. J. (2020, November 12). Retrenchment due to COVID-19 PANDEMIC. Lexology, from <https://www.lexology.com/library/detail.aspx?g=3d042b4d-6646-4f59-b25b-83e631455f87>

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